

DESIGN AND BUILD STEGANOGRPHY WITH PCMPK/B ALGORITHM FOR MESSAGE ENCRYPTION USING VB.NET

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Abstract— Steganography is a method for storing secret messages into container media such as pictures, audio and video texts as if they were just plain pictures. The inserted secret message can not be damaged during the insertion process into the container media. Before the message is inserted, the message is first encrypted using PCMPK / B algorithm. In this explanation it describes the application of steganography using PCMPK / B algorithm for encryption.

Keyword— *steganography, PCMPK/B.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, everything runs fast due to the advantages of using technology that has grown rapidly. With the sophistication of technology now, the main challenge lies in data security while sharing information over the internet network. Therefore, data security techniques are required to avoid irresponsible parties

Secure information security techniques currently use AES encryption. According to Victor Opreescu, AES encryption is a symmetric encryption algorithm, meaning the same key is used for data encryption and decryption. AES encryption method is very good for protecting sensitive data. However, according to Yohan Suryanto, AES encryption if applied to the image image takes a relatively long processing time, it requires a faster encryption and decryption algorithm. Then the exact encryption for the image image is the chaotic permutation algorithm smaller and enlarged (PCMPK / B). The PCMPK / B algorithm is an encryption algorithm that has faster processing for image cintra and has greater space capacity (Suryanto, et al., 2016). Then the required implementation of PCMPK / B algorithm.

Based on the problem, to secure confidential information that has been encrypted steganography technique required. According to Samitha (2016) steganography technique is a method of information security by inserting it into media which can be audio, video, and picture so that the existence of secret information is not seen and as if only in the form of media container and eliminate suspicion to secret message.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Steganography

Steganography is the insertion of confidential data in normal cover media such as digital images, audio, video or text. Input messages should not be damaged during processing at insertion (S & A, 2017).

B. Least Significant Bit (LSB)

LSB modification is a steganographic method that utilizes the fact that LSB modification does not cause the visuals to be highly visible subjectively. LSB is the simplest method by changing the place of LSB image pixels with intensity images replaced by secret message bits (S & A, 2017).

LSB is the most commonly used method. This method is widely used for calculations that are not too complex and hidden messages are quite safe. The strategy uses messages that have been inserted into the media and use least significant bit (LSB) methods. The message bit will be moved to the smallest bit in the container medium.

Figure 1 MSB and LSB

MSB: *Most Significant bit*

LSB: *Least Significant bit.*

A. Chaotic Permutation Multiple Circular Shrinking and Expanding (PCMPK / B)

this algorithm is a chaotic permutation that can satisfy all possible permutations for an element, possibly an element

selected to occupy the i position in a permutation depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Number of Element Choice Each Stage $T(n)$ Permutation N Element. (Suryanto, et al., 2016)

Each permutation stage, involving an increasing number of elements, differs from one element to the previous one. Randomization in this way will result in the possibility of permutation of many elements $n \times (n-1) \times (n-2) \times (n-3) \times (n-4) \times \dots \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 = n$ factorial (Suryanto, et al., 2016).

Figure 3 Visualization of Multiple Shrinking Chaotic Permutations (PCMPK) for N Elements. (Suryanto & Ramli, 2016)

Figure 3 can describe such as :

1. Determine the block size N that will be permuted.
2. Select a Key
3. Perform expanded key, as the movement distance in $N-1$ array. $D_{Key}(i) = Key \bmod (N - i)$ where $i = 1: (N - 1)$
4. Perform the first circular permutation by rotating the N elements clockwise at distance $D_{Key}(1)$.
5. The first index output is saved as the permutation $P(1)$ result and will be omitted from the next circular movement.
6. Perform the second circular permutation by rotating the $N-1$ elements clockwise at distance $D_{Key}(2)$.
7. The second index output is saved as the permutation $P(2)$ result and will be omitted from the next circular movement.
8. Perform steps 6 and 7 until the number of elements is 2 (Suryanto & Ramli, 2016)

Figure 4 Visualization Chaotic Permutation Circular Expanding (PCMPB) for N Elements. (Suryanto & Ramli, 2016)

Meanwhile the PCMPK algorithm can be figure out in Fig. 4 and can be described as follows:

1. Determine the block size N that will be permuted
2. Select the associated Key
3. Perform expanded key, as the movement distance in $N-1$ array. $D_{Key}(i) = Key \bmod (N - i)$ where $i = 1: (N - 1)$
4. Perform the first circular permutation by rotating the last 2 elements counter clockwise at distance $D_{Key}(N - 1)$.
5. Data in index $N-2$ is inserted to the 3 last elements.
6. Perform the second circular permutation by rotating the last 3 elements counter clockwise at distance $D_{Key}(N - 2)$.
7. Data in index $N-3$ is inserted to the 4 last elements.
8. Perform the third circular permutation by rotating the last 4 elements counter clockwise at distance $D_{Key}(N - 3)$.
9. Perform steps 7 and 8 until the number of elements is N

III METHODOLOGY

This research will implement PCMPK / B algorithm in steganography process on image image using VB.NET.

PCMPK/B Algorithm

The PCMPK / B algorithm has two computations, chaotic permutations multiple circular shrinking (PCMPK) used as

encryption and chotic permutations multiple circular expanding (PCMPB) are used as decryption.

PCMPK

$$X_n^k(i) = X(\text{mod}(i + k, n)); n \in Z^+, 0 \leq i < n, 0 \leq k < n \quad (1)$$

$$Y_n = X_{n-j}^{k(j)}(0)]_{j=0}^{n-1}; n \in Z^+, 0 \leq j < n, 0 \leq k < n \wedge k(j) < n - j \quad (2)$$

$$\odot (X_n) = X_{n-j}^{k(j)}(0)]_{j=0}^{n-1} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_n = \odot (X_n) \quad (4)$$

Technique of chaotic permutation multiple circular shringking is mapping set X into n unique factorial used by multiple circular with modulation set of element with modulation equal to the number of elements involved in each round. A rotation shift function of the set X which has n elements and has a shift distance as far as k is described in equation (1). If we take the first element $X_n^{k(0)}(0)$ as permutation element to $Y_n(0)$ and not put in the next round, continue the process and take $X_{n-2}^{k(1)}(0)$ as the permutation element of $Y_n(1)$, $X_{n-2}^{k(2)}$ as $Y_n(2)$ so on until $X_2^{k(n-2)}$ as $Y_n(n - 2)$ and lements that are same of $Y_n(n - 1)$, then permutation of X_n can be rewritten to Y_n according to the equation (2). If \odot selected as an operator of the enlarged multi-permutation defined in equation (3), then equation (2) can be rewritten into equation (4).

```
function Y = ACPMCSM2(X, keys)

NSize = length(X);
kunci = keys;
index = 0;
for n=1:(NSize-1)
    index =mod(index+(kunci(n)),NSize-n+1);
    Y(n) = X(index+1);
    X(index+1) = [];
end
Y(NSize) = X(1);
```

Figure 3.1 PCMPK algorithm on matlab language

Table 3.1 Conversion data to number

	Type of character	Convert into number
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Secret message	JTIK	74 84 73 75
password	1234	49 50 51 52

Table 3.2 Calculation of PCMPK algorithm

Circular -	Code of Matlab	Result of Code	Result
1 Y = 74 84 73 75 Password = 49 50 51 52	$index = \text{mod}(index + (kunci(n)), Nsize - n + 1)$	$\text{mod}(0 + 49, 4 - 1 + 1) = 1$	84
	$Yn = X(index + 1)$	$Y_1 = X(1 + 1) = 84$	
	$X(index + 1) = []$	$X(index + 1) = []$ $X(2) = []$	
2 Y = 74 73 75 Password = 49 50 51 52	$index = \text{mod}(index + (kunci(n)), Nsize - n + 1)$	$\text{mod}(1 + 50, 4 - 2 + 1) = 0$	74
	$Yn = X(index + 1)$	$Y_1 = X(0 + 1) = 74$	
	$X(index + 1) = []$	$X(index + 1) = []$ $X(1) = []$	
3 Y = 73 75 74 Password = 49 50 51 52	$index = \text{mod}(index + (kunci(n)), Nsize - n + 1)$	$\text{mod}(0 + 51, 4 - 3 + 1) = 1$	75
	$Yn = X(index + 1)$	$Y_1 = X(1 + 1) = 75$	
	$X(index + 1) = []$	$X(index + 1) = []$ $X(2) = []$	
4 Y = 73 74 75 Password = 49 50 51 52	$index = \text{mod}(index + (kunci(n)), Nsize - n + 1)$	$\text{mod}(1 + 53, 4 - 4 + 1) = 0$	73
	$Yn = X(index + 1)$	$Y_1 = X(0 + 1) = 73$	
	$X(index + 1) = []$	$X(index + 1) = []$ $X(1) = []$	

The result of PCMPK calculation is the calculation result of each round with the value of 84 74 75 73 and if it is passed into character become TJKI.

PCMPB

$$X_2 = Y_2^{k(n-2)}, Y(n-2, n-1) = X_2 \quad (5)$$

$$X_3 = Y_3^{k(n-3)}, Y(n-3, n-1) = X_3 \quad (6)$$

$$X_n = Y_j^{k(n-j)} \Big|_{j=2}^n; n \in Z^+, 0 \leq j < n, k(n-j) < j \quad (7)$$

$$\odot(Y_n) = Y_j^{k(n-j)} \Big|_{j=2}^n; n \in Z^+, 0 \leq j < n, k(n-j) < j \quad (8)$$

$$X_n = \odot(Y_n) \quad (9)$$

The multi-loop chaotic permutation formula enlarges in the opposite way, to get the X_n set of Y_n done by the rotation method with the number of enlarged elements. The first calculation has a set of Y_n with n elements and defines the last 2 elements as Y_2 , the last 3 elements as Y_3 and so on, and defines the set X_2 as the mapping of X_2 in the first round, then the relationship between X_2 and Y_2 can be written in (5). In the second round, the set X_3 is a mapping of Y_3 corresponding to equation (6). This enlarged loop is continued until it reaches $Y_n(0, n-1)$, which as a whole sets X_n is the mapping of Y_n according to equation (7). If choosing \odot as an enlarged multi-permutation operator defined as equation (8), then (7) can be rewritten as equation (9). According to the equation (4) and equation (9) the multiple permutation expanding is the inverse of the multiple permutation shrinking.

```
function Y = CPMCEM2(X, keys);
NSize = length(X);
for n=1:NSize-2
    Y = X(NSize-n:NSize);
    index = mod(-keys(NSize-n),n+1)+1;
    X(NSize-n:NSize+1-index) = Y(index:n+1);
    if index > 1
        X(NSize+2-index:NSize) = Y(1:index-1);
    end
    Y = X;
end
```

Data hasil PCMPK = 84, 74, 75, 73

Password = 49, 50, 51, 52

Circular n	Code of Matlab	Result of code	Result
1 X = 84, 74, 75, 73 Keys = 49, 50, 51, 52	Y = X(NSize - n: NSize)	Y = X(3: 4) Y = 75, 73	84, 74, 73, 75
	index = mod(-keys(NSize - n), n + 1) + 1	index = mod(-keys(NSize - 1), 1 + 1) + 1 index = mod(-51, 2) + 1 Index = 2	
	X(NSize - n : NSize + 1 - index) = Y(index : n + 1)	X(4-1:4+1-2) = Y(2:1+1) X(3:3)=Y(2) X(3)=73	
2 X = 84, 74, 73, 75 Keys = 49, 50, 51, 52	X(NSize + 2 - index : NSize) = Y(1: index - 1)	X(4+2-2:4) = Y(1:2-1) X(4:4)=Y(1:1) X(4)=75	84, 73, 75, 74
	Y = X(NSize - n: NSize)	Y = X(2: 4) Y = 74, 73, 75	
	index = mod(-keys(NSize - n), n + 1) + 1	index = mod(-keys(NSize - 2), 2 + 1) + 1 index = mod(-50, 3) + 1 index = 2	
3 X = 84, 74, 73, 75 Keys = 49, 50, 51, 52	X(NSize - n : NSize + 1 - index) = Y(index : n + 1)	X(4-2:4+1-2) = Y(2:2+1) X(2:3)=Y(2:3) X(2:3)=73,75	74, 84, 73, 75
	Y = X(NSize - n: NSize)	Y = X(1: 4) Y = 84, 73, 75, 74	
	index = mod(-keys(NSize - n), n + 1) + 1	index = mod(-keys(NSize - 3), 3 + 1) + 1 index = mod(-49, 4) + 1 index = 4	
	X(NSize + 2 - index : NSize) = Y(1: index - 1)	X(4+2-4:4) = Y(1:4-1) X(2:4)=Y(1:3)	
	X(NSize - n : NSize + 1 - index) = Y(index : n + 1)	X(4-3:4+1-4) = Y(4:3+1) X(1:1)=Y(4:4) X(1)=74	

Table 3.3 Calculation of PCMPB algorithm

		$X(2:4) = 84, 73, 75$	
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Figure 6 is the initial view of a steganography application, the user can choose to engage in message insertion or extract messages

Figure 5 Flowchart

In Figure 5 the initial view displays the message insert feature and extracts the message. Insert the selected message, then select the picture in the message insert view. After selecting a picture, input a secret message and password. The application will run the encryption process using PCMPK algorithm, if the secret message or password is not input then there will be a notification to input the secret message and password. Empty secret messages and passwords are inputted. After that click the button paste the message, the message successfully inserted into the cover image will be a stego image and can be saved. Page extract message, choose stego image to be extracted. After that enter the password and then click the extract message button. Stego image will issue an encrypted secret message. After that runs the decryption process using PCMPB algorithm. When successfully a secret message will appear.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Figure 6 Initial view of the application

Figure 7 Initial View Insert Message

Figure 8 The display selects the cover image

Figure 8 appears after the user clicks the image select button, the user is asked to select the cover image with JPEG, BMP, PNG format.

Figure 9 the display after insert cover image

In Figure 9 after the cover image is selected, the image will appear on page extract messages then the user can fill in secret messages and passwords.

Figure 10 Display

In Figure 10 displays a notification that the insertion of the secret message succeeded.

Figure 11 Views To Save Stego Image

Figure 11 is a display after click save, stego image that has been inserted a secret message can be saved with PNG, BMP and JPEG format.

Figure 12 Initial view of message extract

Figure 13 The display chooses the stego image

Figure 13 display after click on select image, and will display the stego image file to be extracted.

Figure 14 The display before click extract

After selecting stego image Figure 14 will display the selected stego image and user input password.

Figure 15 The display after click extract

Figure 15 shows the secret message contained in the stego image after clicking the extract button.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the design of steganography applications using PCMPK / B algorithm for message encryption using VB.NET has been as expected. The system has addressed issues, such as:

1. This Steganography application has been created using VB.NET
2. This Steganography application has used PCMPK algorithm for encryption and decryption of secret messages.

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